

Attitudes toward mathematics through gamification

Ñañez Javier, Nancy
Universidad César Vallejo
Lima, Perú

Matos Lizana, Julio Cesar
Universidad César Vallejo
Lima, Perú

Flores Cisneros, Roxana Milagros
Universidad César Vallejo
Lima, Perú

Montalvo Herrera, Jessie Angiela
Universidad César Vallejo
Lima, Perú

Tocre Fracchia, Jacqueline Milagros
Universidad César Vallejo
Lima, Perú

Abstract

One of the current concerns in the educational context is the poor attitudes towards mathematics, so the present research aimed to evaluate the effect of gamification on attitudes towards mathematics in students of the Cañete 2024 Higher Technological Institute. For this, the methodology was quantitative with a quasi-experimental design and a sample of 40 students divided into two groups: control and experimental, each with 20 students in its composition. To evaluate attitudes towards mathematics, the questionnaire was used, which was validated through expert judgment and with Cronbach's Alpha reliability = 0.914. In relation to the results, significant differences were reported in both groups, but with a greater difference in the experimental group and in coherence with the inferential analysis based on the data extracted from the student's t-test, the impact or positive effect of gamification on attitudes towards mathematics was determined with a value in Cohen's $d = 13.71990$, which demonstrates relevant positive effects.

Keywords—attitude, cognitive, interest, mathematics, motivation

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Problematic Reality

Attitudes towards mathematics represent a great challenge at all educational levels since there is a widespread prejudice in a large percentage of students who consider mathematics as difficult and complicated to learn [1]. In this circumstance, students who have negative attitudes towards mathematics are those who have the most learning difficulties by not understanding numerical concepts or by having difficulty solving more complex problems, which translates into greater anxiety and motivational detachment. However, although mathematics is considered an obstacle, delay in studying or a tendency to drop out, its learning and acquisition of knowledge are an important catalyst for academic success [2]. On the other hand, learning is currently being transformed due to the constant innovation of technologies and innovative methodologies such as gamification [3]. In this scenario, the main motivation of this research lies in the need to promote the use of emerging pedagogical strategies, methods, methodologies such as the

incorporation of gamification with the intention of reducing the barriers that hinder the learning of mathematics and negative attitudes towards them [4]. The application of gamification represents a great challenge since it requires technological and digital capabilities of teachers and the possibility of adopting it for pedagogical practice considering that students have accessibility to it.

Negative attitudes toward mathematics are a global problem. In the Philippines, some students believe that learning mathematics is of little use other than in the fish market [5]. A study conducted in Norway found that more than half of university students found mathematics boring [6]. The problem is also not foreign to Latin America, as is the case of a study reported in Mexico, which revealed that 42.0% of students dislike mathematics, 49.0% of respondents perceived mathematics as not motivating, and a number of negative behaviors led students to perceive mathematics unfavorably [7].

In the Peruvian context, a study conducted at universities in Arequipa revealed that the majority of students, representing 64.0%, presented average attitudes. Furthermore, the study demonstrated deficiencies in the affective attitudes dimension, which supports the idea that, although students are open to learning, they fail to establish an emotional connection with mathematics [8]. In Lima, a study conducted at a private university reported that 96.7% of students demonstrated a moderate level of attitudes toward mathematics. This implies that, for the most part, students, although they find mathematics difficult, do not dislike it, as they accept it as such. Furthermore, these findings show that students often think they cannot handle mathematics, but this does not mean they reject it completely [9]. En la misma línea de resultados, otro estudio efectuado en una universidad pública, reportó que el 84.6% de estudiantes demostraron un nivel regular en sus actitudes hacia las matemáticas, reflejando una actitud más neutral, limitando la capacidad de ver las matemáticas como atractivas o relevantes [10].

At a public technological higher education institute in Cañete, a serious deficiency has been identified in students' mathematical skills, especially in areas related to complex problem-solving and the application of technology. An internal study conducted by the institution in 2023 revealed that only 40% of students achieve a satisfactory level in their mathematical assessments, according to their report cards (Academic Unit Head's Office). This highlights the urgent need to introduce innovative teaching strategies that include the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in the teaching-learning process.

B. Literature Review

Definition of Gamification

Gamification represents a playful pedagogical strategy that involves incorporating game components into learning situations, mediated or implemented by the teacher, thereby modifying traditional teaching-learning processes with the intention of actively engaging and motivating students [11].

Likewise, gamification refers to a teaching-learning technique that uses playful strategies as mechanisms to foster motivation and stimulate learning in a more fun way, taking advantage of the dynamic interaction between teachers and students and the incorporation of goals, rewards, feedback, and other aspects that encourage greater student attention [12].

Similarly, gamification has been considered a game-based learning strategy, which involves the integration of a set of playful elements or game mechanics to engage students in their learning and motivate them so that greater participation translates into student interest in achieving their learning [13].

Gamification also represents a distinct pedagogical method, which transforms the traditional form of interaction that occurs in the learning process, making it more didactic by introducing playful elements, which in turn impacts motivation and also generates an enjoyable learning experience for students [14].

Relevant Gamification Theories

Among the most notable theories is the gamification learning theory, developed by Whitton and Moseley in 2014. It proposes that gamification is not only a strategy to enhance or facilitate the learning process, but also acts as a powerful catalyst, contributing to increased motivation levels. Furthermore, according to this theoretical contribution, gamification triggers students to activate learning regulation behaviors [15].

Likewise, the flow theory developed by Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi is relevant for supporting the application of gamification. This theory proposes that flow is an optimal manifestation of enjoyment or a psychological state of optimal experience. This theory contributes to the objective of implementing gamification by being used as a mechanism based on the inclusion of playful elements and components in learning processes to cause or provoke students' immersion and enjoyment of gamified activities. This implies that gamification is also implemented to generate greater motivation and commitment of students [16].

Among the most important theories is Skinner's positive reinforcement, which explains that a student's behavior can be modified by incorporating playful gamification strategies through positive reinforcements such as rewards, levels, or achievements. This contributes to motivating students by reinforcing behaviors that promote learning and greater participation or involvement [17].

One of the relevant theoretical models for gamification is Yu-kai Chou's Octalysis model, designed based on eight motivational drivers, including achievement, which operates as a driver for challenges, creativity, and feedback. Applied to gamification, this model represents a guided learning mechanism. Therefore, the incorporation of this model is essential to motivate and foster greater engagement with students' learning [18].

Dimensions of Gamification

Gamification was evaluated based on three dimensions: mechanics, dynamics, and components [19]:

The mechanical dimension refers to the elements or rules used to achieve objectives, such as motivation, participation, and learning. They can include points, levels, challenges, rewards, board leaders, among others. These mechanics are flexible tools and can be adapted to specific needs and contexts, offering a wide variety of options for designing gamified experiences [20].

The dynamic dimension refers to the needs that are met as participants engage in a gamified activity. These needs can be related to the game mechanics, interaction with other users, or the narrative created around the gamified proposal. Dynamics are key elements that motivate participants and provide them with a rewarding experience while participating in the activity [20].

The component dimension refers to the elements used to design an activity in the practice of gamification. Components deal with the visual resources such as graphics, music, setting and plot that are displayed and applied in the game [21].

Definition of attitudes towards mathematics

Attitudes are considered as behavioral inclinations that are acquired through learning and developed through experience, which implies an assessment that has an impact on favorable or unfavorable behavior towards an object [22]. Attitudes toward mathematics are a multidimensional construct and have been conceptualized based on three components: emotions, beliefs, and behavioral response. Emotions represent responses of an affective and cognitive nature, linked to mathematical activities. Beliefs denote the perceptions or ideas that students have about mathematics, and behavioral responses are those behavioral actions adopted towards this subject [23]. In relation to positive attitudes, affective components, expectation-value, and confidence in mathematical achievement are integrated [24]. Therefore, positive attitudes are

those that favor the connection with mathematics, which also leads to learning without the expected resistance [25]. Attitudes toward mathematics represent those personal tendencies or inclinations that are externalized favorably or unfavorably towards mathematics [26].

Theories Related to Attitudes Toward Mathematics

Regarding the main theories that contribute to the understanding of this variable, the contributions of the Modified Three-Dimensional Attitude Model developed by Di Martino and Zan in 2010 are detailed. Given the difficulty of assessing attitudes, they designed a model that includes three dimensions: a) the emotional dimension, which describes students' feelings toward mathematics, the importance expressed in terms of likes, preferences, and a series of emotional responses; b) the perspective on mathematics, that is, the perception of tasks, topics, and processes related to mathematics that influence interest or willingness to learn mathematics. This dimension also assesses how students appreciate or show appreciation for the course; and c) the last component refers to perceived competence, which is understood as beliefs about their ability to take on mathematical challenges [27].

Dimensions of attitudes toward mathematics

To measure attitudes toward mathematics, three dimensions are distinguished [28]:

The cognitive dimension represents the set of beliefs, perceptions, and thoughts related to mathematics, which implies an assessment of what mathematics represents in academic life [29].

The affective dimension refers to the feelings, expressions, and emotional reactions linked to mathematics, whose positive assessment reflects an emotional connection with it [30].

The behavioral dimension responds to the predisposition or tendency to react in a particular way [31].

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Method

The method adopted in the research is quantitative and refers to a research strategy that seeks to test hypotheses. This reflects the need for quantification or measurement of variables with the intention of confirming or predicting the phenomena examined [32]. Furthermore, the research is characterized by being applied. This type of research differs from basic research because it transforms basic knowledge into practical applications or interventions that lead to problem-solving [33]. Regarding the design, the research is quasi-experimental, which refers to studies that have two non-randomly selected groups with the intention of verifying that the intervention carried out in the experimental group is effective and positive, unlike the control group, which had a reference condition [34]. Furthermore, these studies are characterized by being longitudinal, which implies follow-up evaluations on more than one occasion [35].

B. Participants

Regarding the population, it consisted of 70 students from the Instituto Superior Tecnológico de Cañete, 2024. The population is understood as the group of elements that share common conditions with which each of these elements is identified [36]. Regarding the inclusion criteria, students of both sexes in the first cycle of mathematics courses at the Instituto Superior Tecnológico de Cañete, 2024, with regular class attendance, were considered. Exclusion criteria included not including students with academic delays due to absences and those who did not provide informed consent. Similarly, the sample consisted of 40 students divided into two groups: 20 representing the control group and 20 for the experimental group. The sample is

conceptualized as the part extracted from the population, whose selection allows for the study of inferences about the topic under study [37].

C. Research Techniques

To evaluate the variable "attitudes toward mathematics," the survey technique was used. This method is considered a method for gathering information on the opinions, perceptions, or behaviors of the people participating in the study or the sample of which they are part [38]. The questionnaire was used as the instrument, which represents the data collection mechanism, that is, a list composed of questions based on indicators and dimensions [39]. Validity refers to the relevance to which the instrument is able to quantify a construct for which it was designed. Content validity represents the degree or extent to which the instrument reflects the content being examined [40]; and reliability is the degree of consistency and coherence of the results [41]. In this particular case, validation was carried out through expert judgment. Regarding the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted, the data examined of which yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.914.

D. Data Analysis

To analyze the data, a database was first created with the survey records in Excel format, and then SPSS version 31 was used to apply descriptive and inferential statistics [42]. Regarding the methods used to process the data, statistics were applied in two stages: the first, from a descriptive perspective, to process the data and obtain information on the frequency distribution. An inferential analysis was conducted in two phases: the first to investigate normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test, performed when the sample size was less than 50 [43]; The second phase, based on these reports, was followed by the Student t-test, which took into account the parametric tests, which indicates that the sample did not have a normal distribution [44].

III. RESULTS

A. Descriptive Results

Attitudes Toward Mathematics

As can be seen in Table I, the mean value in the pretest was the same for the control and experimental groups, so it can be deduced that both groups are quite homogeneous. Furthermore, comparing the pretest and posttest, an increase in the means in both groups can be noted, with the difference being much greater in the EG compared to the CG. Similarly, it can be observed that in the posttest, the value shows substantial differences in the EG compared to the CG, demonstrating improvements in scores.

TABLE I
MEASURES OF CENTRAL TENDENCY IN ATTITUDES TOWARD MATHEMATICS

Groups	Mean	Confidence Interval	Median	Variance	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
GC_Pretest	74.50	[59.84-75.76]	63.00	289.537	17.016	38	104
GE_Pretest	74.50	[67.73-81.27]	70.00	209.000	14.457	57	104
GC_Post_test	83.00	[75.39-90.60]	87.00	264.000	16.248	53	109
GE_Post_test	93.95	[88.98-98.91]	95.50	112.471	10.605	66	109

Note. GC = Control group; EG = Experimental group; CI = 95.0% confidence interval

Cognitive attitudes toward mathematics

Based on the information provided in Table II, slight differences are observed in the pre-test means, with a minimal advantage for the EG ($M = 22.25$) compared to the CG ($M = 20.50$). Therefore, it is assumed that the groups are homogeneous in their cognitive attitudes toward mathematics before the intervention. In the post-test evaluation, the differences become more noticeable, with the CG ($M = 27.50$) scoring more favorably over the CG ($M = 24.85$). Therefore, it can be deduced that both groups improved their cognitive attitudes, but the experimental group that received the gamified mathematics intervention scored higher.

TABLE II
MEASURES OF CENTRAL TENDENCY IN COGNITIVE ATTITUDES TOWARD MATHEMATICS

Groups	Mean	Confidence Interval	Median	Variance	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
GC_Pretest	20.50	[17.71-23.29]	17.50	35.632	5.969	13	33
GE_Pretest	22.25	[19.59-24.91]	23.50	32.408	5.693	14	32
GC_Post_test	24.85	[22.32-27.38]	26.00	29.292	5.412	16	34
GE_Post_test	27.50	[25.44-29.56]	29.00	19.421	4.407	16	32

Note. GC = Control group; EG = Experimental group; CI = 95.0% confidence interval

Affective Attitudes Toward Mathematics

Table III shows that, when comparing the pretest means, there are differences between the two groups, implying that they were not homogeneous before the intervention. Similarly, there are differences in the posttest means that favor the experimental group, with $M = 30.50$ compared to the control group, with $M = 27.05$. Likewise, a within-group analysis showed that both groups showed differences, suggesting an increase in the level of affective attitudes toward mathematics.

TABLE III
MEASURES OF CENTRAL TENDENCY IN AFFECTIVE ATTITUDES TOWARD MATHEMATICS

Groups	Mean	Confidence Interval	Median	Variance	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
GC_Pretest	21.45	[18.53-24.37]	20.00	38.997	6.245	10	32
GE_Pretest	24.20	[21.55-26.85]	21.50	31.958	5.653	18	34
GC_Post_test	27.05	[24.62-29.48]	27.00	26.892	5.186	18	34
GE_Post_test	30.50	[27.86-33.14]	31.00	31.737	5.634	19	38

Note. GC = Control group; EG = Experimental group; CI = 95.0% confidence interval

Behavioral Attitudes Toward Mathematics

Table IV shows differences in the pretest means, with a slight advantage for the experimental group ($M = 28.05$) compared to the control group ($M = 25.85$). Furthermore, differences are noted in the posttest, with higher mean scores for the EG ($M = 35.95$) compared to the CG ($M = 31.10$). It is also evident that both the experimental and control groups showed increases in the mean, demonstrating changes or improvements in behavioral attitudes toward mathematics.

TABLE IV
MEASURES OF CENTRAL TENDENCY IN BEHAVIORAL ATTITUDES TOWARD MATHEMATICS

Groups	Mean	Confidence Interval	Median	Variance	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
GC_Pretest	25.85	[22.54-29.16]	24.00	50.134	7.081	13	40
GE_Pretest	28.05	[24.57-31.53]	24.00	55.418	7.444	21	40
GC_Post_test	31.10	[27.59-34.61]	31.50	56.305	7.504	19	43
GE_Post_test	35.95	[33.40-38.50]	36.50	29.734	5.453	23	43

Note. GC = Control group; EG = Experimental group; CI = 95.0% confidence interval

B. Inferential Results

Normality Test

Table V shows the results of the normality test performed using the Shapiro-Wilk statistic. Significance reports for the attitude toward mathematics variable in both the pretest and posttest are values greater than 0.05, thus implying the use of parametric tests to test the hypothesis.

TABLE V
SHAPIRO-WILK NORMALITY TEST REPORT

	Pretest			Post test		
	Statistics	gl	Sig.	Statistics	gl	Sig.
Attitude toward mathematics GC	0.939	20	0.226	0.952	20	0.396
Attitude toward mathematics GE	0.912	20	0.068	0.949	20	0.357
Cognitive attitude GC	0.843	20	0.004	0.944	20	0.288
Cognitive attitude GE	0.910	20	0.065	0.772	20	0.000
Affective attitude GC	0.926	20	0.130	0.922	20	0.106
Affective attitude GE	0.843	20	0.004	0.928	20	0.143
Behavioral attitude GC	0.843	20	0.004	0.943	20	0.270
Behavioral attitude GE	0.693	20	0.000	0.949	20	0.359

C. Hypothesis Formulation

H1: Gamification has positive effects on students' attitudes toward mathematics.

H1a: Gamification has positive effects on students' cognitive attitudes toward mathematics.

H2a: Gamification has positive effects on students' affective attitudes toward mathematics.

H3a: Gamification has positive effects on students' behavioral attitudes toward mathematics.

D. Hypothesis Testing

General Hypothesis Testing

Table VI shows the intergroup analysis report in independent samples, with a pretest significance value greater than 0.05. Therefore, it can be inferred that no significant differences were found in the pretest. On the contrary, as observed in the posttest, after the gamification intervention in the experimental group, significant differences were observed according to Sig. = 0.008, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the H_a is accepted, which shows significant differences favoring the experimental group and demonstrates that the gamified sessions are positive.

TABLE VI
INTERGROUP COMPARISON BEFORE AND AFTER THE INTERVENTION

		t	gl	Significance		$\Delta \bar{x}$	SE $\Delta \bar{x}$	IC al 95%	
				One-way P	Two-way P			Inf.	Sup.
Pretest	Equal variances are assumed	-1.342	38	.094	.188	-6.700	4.993	-16.807	3.407
	Equal variances are not assumed	-1.342	37.034	.094	.188	-6.700	4.993	-16.816	3.416
Post test	Equal variances are assumed	-2.524	38	.008	.016	-10.950	4.338	-19.733	-2.166
	Equal variances are not assumed	-2.524	32.702	.008	.017	-10.950	4.338	-19.780	-2.119

Note. $\Delta \bar{x}$ = Difference in means, SE $\Delta \bar{x}$ = Standard error of the difference; Inf. = Lower bound; Sup. = Upper bound

According to the information in Table VII, it is observed that the Cohen's d value = 13.71990. If this value is greater than 0.8, the effect size is substantial, thus confirming that gamification significantly influences attitudes toward mathematics.

TABLE VII
IMPACT FACTOR OF GAMIFICATION IMPLEMENTATION

		Standardizer ^a	Point estimate 95%	confidence Interval 95%	
				Lower	Upper
Intervention	d de Cohen	13.71990	-.798	-1.438	-.148
	Corrección de Hedges	13.99832	-.782	-1.410	-.145
	Delta de Glass	10.60524	-1.033	-1.722	-.322

Table VIII shows the paired differences for both the control group and the experimental group, observing the existence of significant differences according to Sig. < 0.05, which implies that in both groups there were significant differences in both the control group and the experimental group, however, it is the experimental group that noticed more substantial improvements as evidenced by the difference in means. This means that the implementation of gamification represented a favorable resource for attitudes towards mathematics.

TABLE VIII
COMPARATIVE INTRAGROUP ANALYSIS FOR GC AND GE

	Paired Differences			IC al 95%		Statistics	gl	Significance	
	\bar{x}	s	SE	Inf.	Sup.			One-way P	Two-way P
PretestGC - PosttestGC	-15.200	10.846	2.425	-20.276	-10.124	-6.267	19	<.001	<.001
PretestGE - PosttestGE	-19.450	10.410	2.328	-24.322	-14.578	-8.356	19	<.001	<.001

Nota. \bar{x} = Media; s = Desv. Estándar; SE = Media de error estándar; Inf = Límite inferior; Sup = Límite superior; gl = grados de libertad

Specific Hypothesis Test 1

According to the report in Table IX of the intergroup analysis in independent samples, the significance level for the pretest is greater than 0.05, so it can be inferred that no significant differences were observed in the pretest. On the contrary, as observed in the posttest, after the gamification intervention in the experimental group, significant differences were observed according to Sig. = 0.049, which is less than 0.05. This implies the existence of significant differences favoring the experimental group and demonstrates that the intervention of gamified sessions is positive for cognitive attitudes toward mathematics.

TABLE IX
INTERGROUP COMPARISON BEFORE AND AFTER THE INTERVENTION

		t	gl	Significance		$\Delta \bar{x}$	SE $\Delta \bar{x}$	IC al 95%	
				One-way P	Two-way P			Inf.	Sup.
Pretest	Equal variances are assumed	-0.949	38	.174	.349	-1.750	1.844	-5.484	1.984
	Equal variances are not assumed	-0.949	37.915	.174	.349	-1.750	1.844	-5.484	1.984
Post test	Equal variances are assumed	-1.698	38	.049	.098	-2.650	1.561	-5.809	.509
	Equal variances are not assumed	-1.698	36.501	.049	.098	-2.650	1.561	-5.814	.514

Note. $\Delta \bar{x}$ = Difference in means, SE $\Delta \bar{x}$ = Standard error of the difference; Inf. = Lower bound; Sup. = Upper bound

According to the information in Table X, it is observed that the Cohen's d value = 4.935, with this value greater than 0.8, establishes that the effect size is substantial, thus confirming that gamification has a significant and positive influence on cognitive attitudes toward mathematics.

TABLE X
IMPACT FACTOR OF GAMIFICATION IMPLEMENTATION

		Standardizer ^a	Point estimate 95%	confidence Interval 95%	
				Lower	Superior
Intervention	d de Cohen	4.935	-.537	-1.165	.098
	Corrección de Hedges	5.035	-.526	-1.142	.096
	Delta de Glass	4.407	-.601	-1.242	.054

Specific Hypothesis Test 2

According to the intergroup analysis report in independent samples, the significance level for the pretest was greater than 0.05, suggesting that no significant differences were found in the pretest. In contrast, as observed in the posttest, after the gamification intervention in the experimental group, significant differences were observed, with Sig. = 0.026 being less than 0.05. This implied acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. Therefore, significant differences favoring the experimental group are evident, demonstrating that the gamified sessions have a positive effect on affective attitudes toward mathematics.

TABLE XI
INTERGROUP COMPARISON BEFORE AND AFTER THE INTERVENTION

		t	gl	Significance		$\Delta \bar{x}$	SE $\Delta \bar{x}$	IC al 95%	
				One-way P	Two-way P			Inf.	Sup.
Pretest	Equal variances are assumed	-1.460	38	.076	.153	-2.750	1.884	-6.563	1.063
	Equal variances are not assumed	-1.460	37.630	.076	.153	-2.750	1.884	-6.564	1.064
Post test	Equal variances are assumed	-2.015	38	.026	.051	-3.450	1.712	-6.916	.016
	Equal variances are not assumed	-2.015	37.742	.026	.051	-3.450	1.712	-6.917	.017

Note. $\Delta \bar{x}$ = Difference in means, $SE\Delta \bar{x}$ = Standard error of the difference; Inf. = Lower bound; Sup. = Upper bound

According to the information in Table XII, it is observed that the value of Cohen's $d = 5.414$, this value being greater than 0.8, it is established that the effect size is substantial, so it is verified that gamification has a significant influence and with a positive effect on affective attitudes towards mathematics.

TABLE XII
IMPACT FACTOR OF GAMIFICATION IMPLEMENTATION

		Standardizer ^a	Point estimate 95%	confidence Interval 95%	
				Lower	Superior
Intervention	d de Cohen	5.414	-.637	-1.269	.003
	Corrección de Hedges	5.524	-.625	-1.244	.003
	Delta de Glass	5.634	-.612	-1.254	.044

Specific Hypothesis Test 3

According to the report in Table XIII of the intergroup analysis in independent samples, the pretest shows a significance level greater than 0.05, so it is inferred that no significant differences were found in the pretest. On the contrary, as observed in the posttest, after the gamification intervention in the experimental group, significant differences were observed according to Sig. = 0.012, which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis is accepted, and significant differences are evident in favor of the experimental group, demonstrating that the intervention of gamified sessions has a positive effect on behavioral attitudes toward mathematics.

TABLE XIII
INTERGROUP COMPARISON BEFORE AND AFTER THE INTERVENTION

		t	gl	Significance		$\Delta \bar{x}$	$SE\Delta \bar{x}$	IC al 95%	
				One-way P	Two-way P			Inf.	Sup.
Pretest	Equal variances are assumed	-.958	38	.172	.344	-2.200	2.297	-6.851	2.451
	Equal variances are not assumed	-.958	37.905	.172	.344	-2.200	2.297	-6.851	2.451
Post test	Equal variances are assumed	-2.338	38	.012	.025	-4.850	2.074	-9.048	-.6511
	Equal variances are not assumed	-2.338	34.691	.013	.025	-4.850	2.074	-9.062	-.6379

Note. $\Delta \bar{x}$ = Difference in means, $SE\Delta \bar{x}$ = Standard error of the difference; Inf. = Lower bound; Sup. = Upper bound

According to the information in Table XIV on the effect size, it is observed that the value of Cohen's $d = 6.55894$, this value being greater than 0.8, it is established that the effect size is substantial, so it is verified that gamification has a significant influence and a substantial effect on behavioral attitudes towards mathematics.

TABLE XIV
IMPACT FACTOR OF GAMIFICATION IMPLEMENTATION

		Standardizer ^a	Point estimate 95%	confidence Interval 95%	
				Lower	Superior
Intervention	d de Cohen	6.55894	-.739	-1.376	-.093
	Corrección de Hedges	6.69205	-.725	-1.349	-.091
	Delta de Glass	5.45291	-.889	-1.560	-.199

IV. DISCUSSION

After the inferential analysis comparing the groups before and after the intervention with gamified classes, significant differences were reported in the post-test, leading to the assumption that the gamification intervention positively contributed to improving attitudes toward mathematics. Furthermore, the impact factor obtained using Student's t-test reflects a Cohen's d value of 13.71990, which exceeds the value of 0.80, confirming the high impact of gamification. From these results, it can be inferred that the incorporation of gamification into learning sessions, using resources such as Mathigon, Nearpod, and Wordwall, has contributed to improving student experiences, which has positively contributed to increasing students' interest and motivation in mathematics. These results reflect that the gamified intervention works as a mechanism to activate students' desire to participate and learn as if they were playing a game, since gamified sessions involve the application of elements such as game dynamics and mechanics in the sessions. The results are related to the research carried out by Lee et al. [45], whose objective was focused on evaluating the effectiveness of gamification in mathematics, however their results showed that the differences were minimal despite the fact that the components of gamification contributed positively generating greater commitment and motivation for mathematics. Furthermore, the results are supported by Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi's flow theory, which explains that gamification is a strategy in which the introduction of game components contributes to generating the conditions for the student to experience flow, so that, as a result of these experiences, which are gratifying due to the playful aspects immersed in the educational processes, contribute to increasing motivation [16].

Likewise, the study is supported by the theory of didactic situations of Brousseau and Artigue, which specify that, to obtain positive results in the learning of mathematics, there must be appropriate didactic situations such as gamification, which used by teachers creates favorable experiences to increase the interest and motivation of students [46]. Likewise, the Theory of learning through gamification allows us to understand the results since, according to Whitton and Moseley, learning is not achieved by the mere application of gamification as a didactic or pedagogical input, but because gamification represents a medium in which students' behaviors are activated. That is, gamification is a catalyst for playful characteristics and will influence students' motivation and learning to the extent that they understand and use the information [15].

Likewise, for hypothesis 1, the effect of gamification on the cognitive dimension of attitudes toward mathematics was verified by reporting that there are significant intergroup differences in the post-test according to Sig. < 0.05 , which reflects a positive change in attitudes toward mathematics in the cognitive dimension after applying gamification, whose effect was determined by Cohen's d being its value = 4.935, so it was also verified that gamification has positive effects on cognitive attitudes toward mathematics. The findings are related to Hamidah et al. [47], who after implementing gamification in the mathematics course using Quizizz and other tools, verified positive effects on motivation. These results are due to the fact that gamification generates an environment whose experience simulates gamified environments, so learning is an experience similar to what playing produces. These experiences make the mathematics class no longer boring, and on the contrary, it is dynamic, active, recreational, which stimulates the student, increasing their motivation. Similarly, the findings are consistent with Zabala et al. [48], whose research examined the effect of gamification on motivation towards mathematics in mathematics students at a university.

Likewise, for hypothesis 2, it was possible to verify that gamification presents positive effects on the affective dimension of attitudes towards mathematics where it was observed that there are significant differences in the post test based on Sig. = 0.026 with Sig. < 0.05 , which shows that gamification significantly influences affective attitudes towards mathematics. Likewise, the impact factor was verified, which was equal to 5.414, which reflects a positive effect. The results are consistent with the study carried

out by Zabala et al. [48], who have developed a program of strategies to motivate students in university mathematics. This study, which was experimental, managed to demonstrate positive implications of the implementation of gamification, especially in motivation, which suggests an important affective involvement of the student with their learning mediated by gamification. Likewise, the findings obtained are related to the study by Sami and Ercag [49], who evaluated the effect of gamification on the learning of mathematics, proving that gamified strategies through the Educhall website contribute to an increase in motivation and affective attitudes towards learning mathematics.

Likewise, for hypothesis 3, it was specified by establishing the effect of gamification on behavioral attitudes towards mathematics, it was verified through intergroup analysis carried out by applying the Student's t test that there are significant differences in the post test with favorable results for the experimental group that was the one that received gamification as part of their learning process in the area of mathematics with the intention of achieving that students have more positive attitudes. In addition, the impact factor obtained through Cohen's d was equal to 6.55894, which shows positive effects of the gamification intervention on behavioral attitudes towards mathematics in the experimental group. The results are consistent with the study by Wahba et al. [50], who verified the effect of the use of the GPT chat on attitudes towards statistics in university students. This research, although not explicitly addressing gamification as an intervention, can be compared to GPT chat as a way of engaging students in learning through the use of technology. The results are also consistent with the study by Angeles [51], who has argued that gamification implemented in mathematics courses has important contributions as it allows higher education students to become motivated and therefore change or adopt more proactive behaviors in learning mathematics.

Based on the findings of this researcher, gamified sessions, which involve the implementation of playful strategies in learning contexts, focus more on capturing students' attention, encouraging them to participate and to have more direct and spontaneous feedback, which contributes to improving aspects such as responsibility, motivation and, above all, participation behaviors, competitiveness, and performance. Similarly, the results are consistent with the study by Zavala et al. [52], who reported that the use of technologies such as gamification has positive effects on improving mathematical skills. According to these researchers, the use of these tools contributes to the student making their learning more beneficial. Likewise, the results are consistent with the study by Anicama [53], who carried out a quasi-experimental investigation to demonstrate that gamification favors academic performance in mathematics, demonstrating that for students who benefit from gamification to achieve better results, gamification focuses on behavioral aspects, which encourages the student to participate, be motivated and get involved in mathematics. After applying gamification, this researcher demonstrated that the experimental group was the one that benefited the most from improvements in motivation towards mathematics than the control group that received the mathematics learning sessions in a traditional way.

The research by Lee et al. [45], is consistent with the results and provides a relevant analysis on how gamification can influence university students' attitudes towards mathematics. According to their quasi-experimental study, by applying gamification in the experimental group, students benefit from a more dynamic, entertaining learning environment that invites participation, improving not only the learning experiences, but also improving attitudes. In short, the results have been supported by various research studies and it has been verified that gamification has positive effects on attitudes towards mathematics. However, it should be noted that gamification is the driving mechanism due to its playful strategy immersed in its process, which implies that learning sessions have playful strategies where students actively participate since it has important effects on the motivational, participatory, attitudinal, interactional and feedback aspects [2].

V. CONCLUSIONS

It was concluded that gamification has a positive effect on attitudes toward mathematics. This finding is supported by the significance level of less than 0.05 obtained in the intergroup comparison of the post-test, which reflected significant differences. The effect was determined by Cohen's $d = 13.71990$, reflecting a positive effect of gamification on attitudes toward mathematics in students at a technical college. Similarly, it was concluded that gamification has positive effects on the cognitive, affective, and behavioral dimensions of mathematics in students.

Regarding the limitations of this research, inherent to its quasi-experimental nature, the lack of random selection of study participants led to a closer look to observe that gamification contributes to improving attitudes toward mathematics in the experimental group. The experimental and control groups correspond to groups of students from two different sections, which could be reflected in their differences in preexisting characteristics, with slight differences, as reported in the analysis of the measures of central tendency.

As a final reflection, it can be mentioned that the use of technology in teaching and learning processes is currently expanding, with gamification being one of the most relevant topics due to the way in which game dynamics are incorporated into learning contexts, generating rewarding experiences compared to traditional or rote methodologies.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Jing, K. Wang, F. Chen, y A. Bicer, «A CAVE Survey for Measuring Mathematics Attitudes Based on the Characteristics of Students in Mainland China», *Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 15, n.º 4, p. 412, 2025, doi: 10.3390/bs15040412.
- [2] C. Tan, T. Ramasamy, C. Tan, y A. Koo, «Influence of conversational agent on students' attitude toward mathematics», *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching and Learning*, 2025, doi: 10.1108/JRIT-09-2024-0234.
- [3] O. Borrás, «Aplicando gamificación analógica y digital en ingeniería: chocolate y Kahoot!», en *Experiencias de innovación educativa aplicada a la formación del profesorado*, 2025. Accedido: 20 de agosto de 2025. [En línea]. Disponible en: <http://www.dykinson.com/libros/experiencias-de-innovacion-educativa-aplicada-a-la-formacion-del-profesorado/9788410708716/>
- [4] J. Ordoñez y U. Durán, «Gamificación con herramientas tecnológicas aplicada en contenidos de Cálculo: Español», *Revista Científica Sinapsis*, vol. 26, n.º 1, 2025, doi: 10.37117/s.v26i1.1142.
- [5] M. A. Langoban, R. G. Tan, y L. S. Lomibao, «Why is there a Need to Foster Positive Attitude Among Learners in Learning Mathematics?», *Journal of Innovations in Teaching and Learning*, vol. 3, n.º 1, Art. n.º 1, jul. 2023, doi: 10.12691/jitl-3-1-7.
- [6] L. Opstad, «Business students' attitudes towards mathematics and performance in business mathematics: A case study of a Norwegian business school», *Contemporary Mathematics and Science Education*, vol. 5, n.º 1, 2024, doi: 10.30935/conmaths/14112.
- [7] A. Trejo y C. Ponce, «Actitudes hacia las matemáticas en los estudiantes de primer grado de la carrera de médico cirujano», *Ciencia Latina Revista Científica Multidisciplinar*, vol. 9, n.º 1, pp. 5647-5669, feb. 2025, doi: 10.37811/cl_rcm.v9i1.16243.
- [8] F. Ceballos *et al.*, «Attitudes Towards Mathematics in Undergraduate Students of Accounting and Administrative Sciences in Peru», *Journal of Higher Education Theory and Practice*, vol. 23, n.º 12, jul. 2023, doi: 10.33423/jhetp.v23i12.6240.
- [9] M. Ricaldi, «Attitudes towards mathematics in university students», *Horizontes Revista de Investigación en Ciencias de la Educación*, vol. 8, n.º 33, pp. 615-624, jun. 2024, doi: 10.33996/revistahorizontes.v8i33.746.

- [10] A. Herrera, M. Cumpa, K. Llanos, y E. Cerna, «Attitudes towards mathematics and learning approaches in university students», *Revista de Ciencias Sociales*, vol. 30, n.º 4, pp. 31-41, dic. 2024, doi: 10.31876/rcs.v30i4.42989.
- [11] D. Antun, «Análisis de la gamificación en los procesos de enseñanza universitarios», *MQRInvestigar*, vol. 9, n.º 2, 2025, doi: 10.56048/MQR20225.9.2.2025.e462.
- [12] M. Vital, «Gamificación en el aprendizaje», *Vida Científica Boletín Científico de la Escuela Preparatoria No. 4*, vol. 13, n.º 25, pp. 26-28, 2025, doi: 10.29057/prepa4.v13i25.13988.
- [13] F. Martillo y D. Ortega, «Gamificación y el rendimiento de los estudiantes: un estudio comparativo», *MQRInvestigar*, vol. 9, n.º 1, 2025, doi: 10.56048/MQR20225.9.1.2025.e427.
- [14] M. Camargo y J. Herrera, «El impacto de la Inteligencia Artificial y la Gamificación en la Educación Contable», *ASCE*, vol. 4, n.º 1, pp. 120-133, 2025, doi: 10.70577/ASCE/120.133/2025.
- [15] L. Margallo *et al.*, «Effectiveness of Quizizz on Students' Learning Motivation and Engagement in a Filipino Class», *East Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, vol. 2, n.º 9, pp. 3719-3734, 2023, doi: 10.55927/eajmr.v2i9.5560.
- [16] D. Kleiber, «The legacy of Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi for leisure studies: An introduction to this special 'tribute' issue», *Journal of Leisure Research*, vol. 55, n.º 5, pp. 589-599, 2024, doi: 10.1080/00222216.2024.2373989.
- [17] A. Mendoza, «Los programas de gamificación en la educación. Revisión sistemática», *EPISTEME KOINONIA*, vol. 8, n.º 16, pp. 209-226, 2025, doi: 10.35381/e.k.v8i16.4567.
- [18] D. Lujé, J. Campoverde, y M. Huila, *Gamificación como Estrategia Potenciadora de Habilidades Cognitivas y Socioemocionales*. Editorial SAGA, 2025. [En línea]. Disponible en: <https://libros.editorialsaga.com/index.php/saga/catalog/book/14>
- [19] D. V. Ramos Morales y R. Pablo Huamani, «La gamificación como estrategia de enseñanza y las habilidades sociales en estudiantes de enfermería en una universidad privada de Lima», *Ciencia Latina Revista Científica Multidisciplinar*, vol. 6, n.º 6, pp. 11321-11335, 2022, doi: 10.37811/cl_rcm.v6i6.4202.
- [20] R. S. Contreras Espinosa y J. L. Eguía Gómez, *Gamificación en aulas universitarias*. Institut de la Comunicació, 2016. Accedido: 15 de diciembre de 2023. [En línea]. Disponible en: <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/libro?codigo=874731>
- [21] K. O. Sánchez, «La gamificación una técnica para motivar y potencializar el aprendizaje», *Formación Estratégica*, vol. 4, n.º 01, pp. 125-140, jun. 2022, [En línea]. Disponible en: <https://www.formacionestrategica.com/index.php/foes/article/view/60>
- [22] C. Butto, A. Leiva, y O. García, «Actitudes hacia las matemáticas con el uso de la tecnología: un estudio en educación secundaria», *Horizontes pedagógicos*, vol. 26, n.º 1, pp. 51-61, 2024, doi: 10.33881/0123-8264.hop.26106.
- [23] A. Stone, «Exploring the Impact of the Corequisite Classroom Climate on Students' Attitudes Toward Mathematics», *International Journal of Research in Undergraduate Mathematics Education*, vol. 11, n.º 1, pp. 91-115, 2025, doi: 10.1007/s40753-023-00226-y.
- [24] C. Yang y L. Tsai, «Positive Attitudes Toward Mathematics and Big-Fish-Little-Pond Effects Among Eighth Grade Taiwanese Students», *SAGE Open*, vol. 14, n.º 4, 2024, doi: 10.1177/21582440241300187.
- [25] B. García, I. Méndez, y J. García, «Evolución de las actitudes hacia las matemáticas en estudiantes universitarios», *European Journal of Child Development, Education and Psychopathology*, vol. 10, n.º 1, pp. 1-10, 2022, doi: 10.32457/ejpad.v10i1.2069.
- [26] J. Zamora, «Las actitudes hacia la matemática, el desarrollo social, el nivel educativo de la madre y la autoeficacia como factores asociados al rendimiento académico en la matemática», *Uniciencia*, vol. 34, n.º 1, pp. 74-87, 2020, doi: 10.15359/ru.34-1.5.

- [27] M. Regista Cahyani, E. Erlina, I. Lestari, M. Masriani, y M. Ulfah, «Measuring meaningful learning through the experience of chemistry education students' in the basics of analytical chemistry practicum», *Jurnal Pendidikan Kimia*, vol. 16, pp. 168-175, ago. 2024, doi: 10.24114/jpkim.v16i2.57849.
- [28] A. A. Romero y E. D. Angeles, «Flipped Classroom in a Digital Learning Space: Its Effect on the Students' Attitude Toward Mathematics», *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, vol. 22, n.º 1, ene. 2023, [En línea]. Disponible en: <https://www.ijlter.org/index.php/ijlter/article/view/6677>
- [29] C. Quiza, F. Gallegos, C. Achata, J. Tumi, y I. Acero, «Actitudes y competencias en matemáticas de estudiantes en formación docente en el sur de Perú», *Horizontes Revista de Investigación en Ciencias de la Educación*, vol. 8, n.º 33, pp. 727-735, jun. 2024, doi: 10.33996/revistahorizontes.v8i33.756.
- [30] A. Ortega, J. Saavedra, y J. Gavidia, *Aprendizaje cooperativo y desarrollo de actitudes frente a la matemática en estudiantes de secundaria, Huánuco-Perú*. 2023. Accedido: 18 de abril de 2025. [En línea]. Disponible en: <https://atenaeditora.com.br/catalogo/ebook/aprendizaje-cooperativo-y-desarrollo-de-actitudes-frente-a-la-matematica-en-estudiantes-de-secundaria-huanuco-peru>
- [31] I. Gómez, *Matemática emocional: Los afectos en el aprendizaje matemático*. Narcea Ediciones, 2023.
- [32] J. Charry y S. Parra, *Manual de Metodología de la Investigación y Principios en Publicación Científica*. Editorial Uninavarra, 2018. [En línea]. Disponible en: https://arbapublishing.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/metodologia_de-investigacion.pdf
- [33] M. Hadi, C. Martel, F. Huayta, R. Rojas, y J. Arias, *Metodología de la investigación: Guía para el proyecto de tesis*. Instituto Universitario de Innovación Ciencia y Tecnología Inudi Perú, 2023. [En línea]. Disponible en: <https://editorial.inudi.edu.pe/index.php/editorialinudi/catalog/book/82>
- [34] C. Carmona, *Investigación cuantitativa. Claves para estudiantes universitarios*. Fondo Editorial Universidad Católica Luis Amigó, 2024. [En línea]. Disponible en: <https://editorial.ucatolicaluisamigo.edu.co/index.php/editorial/catalog/book/222>
- [35] M. Medina, D. Hurtado, J. Muñoz, D. Ochoa, y G. Izundegui, *Método mixto de investigación: Cuantitativo y cualitativo*. Instituto Universitario de Innovación Ciencia y Tecnología Inudi Perú, 2023. [En línea]. Disponible en: <https://editorial.inudi.edu.pe/index.php/editorialinudi/catalog/book/118>
- [36] M. Moscoso, M. Moreno, N. Moscoso, y R. Armijos, *Metodología de la investigación científica y su aplicación en las ciencias agropecuarias*. La Caracola Editores, 2022. [En línea]. Disponible en: <http://cimogsys.esPOCH.edu.ec/direccion-publicaciones/public/docs/books/2022-05-17-201333-Metodologi%CC%81a%20de%20la%20investigacio%CC%81n%20cienti%CC%81fica.pdf>
- [37] J. Hinojosa, *Proyecto de tesis: guía práctica para investigación cuantitativa*. 2024. [En línea]. Disponible en: <https://downloads.editoracientifica.com.br/books/978-65-5360-556-5.pdf>
- [38] J. Aguilar, N. Chariguamán, M. Moscoso, y S. Calderón, *La Estadística como una Herramienta en la Metodología Científica*. 2022. [En línea]. Disponible en: <http://cimogsys.esPOCH.edu.ec/direccion-publicaciones/public/docs/books/2023-01-18-130629-L2022-005.pdf>
- [39] J. Niño y M. Mendoza, *La investigación científica en el contexto académico*. Infinite Study, 2021. [En línea]. Disponible en: https://www.google.com.pe/books/edition/La_investigaci%C3%B3n_cient%C3%ADfica_en_el_cont/B7koEAAAQBAJ?hl=es&gbpv=0
- [40] H. Naupas, E. Mejia, I. Trujillo, H. Romero, W. Medina, y E. Novoa, *Metodología de la investigación total: Cuantitativa – Cualitativa y redacción de tesis*, 6.^a ed. Ediciones de la U, 2023. [En línea]. Disponible en: https://www.google.com.pe/books/edition/Metodolog%C3%ADa_de_la_investigaci%C3%B3n_total/djDEAAAQBAJ?hl=es&gbpv=0

- [41] R. Hernández y C. Mendoza, *Metodología de la investigación: las rutas cuantitativa, cualitativa y mixta*. McGraw-Hill Interamericana, 2018. [En línea]. Disponible en: https://www.google.com.pe/books/edition/METODOLOG%C3%8DA_DE_LA_INVESTIGACI%C3%93N/5A2QDwAAQBAJ?hl=es
- [42] K. Orellana y J. Cañarte, *Bioestadística aplicada a investigaciones científicas en Salud*. Repositorio MAWIL, 2022. [En línea]. Disponible en: <https://mawil.us/repositorio/index.php/academico/catalog/book/5>
- [43] M. Escobar, E. Fernández, y F. Bernardi, *Análisis de datos con Stata*, 3.^a ed. CIS- Centro de Investigaciones Sociológicas, 2021. [En línea]. Disponible en: https://www.google.com.pe/books/edition/An%C3%A1lisis_de_datos_con_Stata/uMIQEAAAQBAJ?hl=es&gbpv=0
- [44] M. Martínez, A. Sánchez, E. Toledo, y J. Faulin, *Bioestadística amigable*. Elsevier Health Sciences, 2020. [En línea]. Disponible en: https://www.google.com.pe/books/edition/Bioestad%C3%ADstica_amigable/C8rSDwAAQBAJ?hl=es&gbpv=0
- [45] J. Lee, C. Pyon, y J. Woo, «Digital Twin for Math Education: A Study on the Utilization of Games and Gamification for University Mathematics Education», *Electronics*, vol. 12, n.º 15, p. 3207, 2023, doi: 10.3390/electronics12153207.
- [46] P. Da Silva y F. Vieira, «Didactic engineering supporting the use of gamification applied to the teaching of arithmetic operations», *Al-Jabar : Jurnal Pendidikan Matematika*, vol. 14, n.º 2, pp. 545-556, 2023, doi: 10.24042/ajpm.v14i2.18125.
- [47] Hamidah, J. Kusuma, y P. Sari, «Application Of Quizizz-Assisted Gamification Model to Students' Mathematical Communication Skills and Learning Motivation», *Jurnal Derivat: Jurnal Matematika dan Pendidikan Matematika*, vol. 11, n.º 2, pp. 257-268, 2024, doi: 10.31316/jderivat.v10i2.6597.
- [48] S. Zabala, L. García, E. Arciniegas, J. Reina, B. Benito, y A. Darder, «Strengthening Motivation in the Mathematical Engineering Teaching Processes – A Proposal from Gamification and Game-Based Learning», *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, vol. 16, n.º 06, pp. 4-19, 2021, doi: 10.3991/ijet.v16i06.16163.
- [49] O. Sami y E. Ercag, «The impact of applying challenge-based gamification program on students' learning outcomes: Academic achievement, motivation and flow», *Education and Information Technologies*, vol. 28, n.º 8, pp. 10053-10078, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s10639-023-11585-z.
- [50] F. Wahba, A. Ajlouni, y M. Abumosa, «The impact of ChatGPT-based learning statistics on undergraduates' statistical reasoning and attitudes toward statistics», *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, vol. 20, n.º 7, 2024, doi: 10.29333/ejmste/14726.
- [51] R. Angeles, «La gamificación: impacto en el aula y autonomía de los estudiantes», *Journal of the Academy*, n.º 10, pp. 171-199, 2024, doi: 10.47058/joa10.9.
- [52] D. Zavala, K. Muñoz, J. Cobos, y G. Correa, «TIC y el fortalecimiento de competencias matemáticas en estudiantes de pedagogía de la enseñanza matemática», *Horizontes. Revista de Investigación en Ciencias de la Educación*, vol. 5, n.º 21, pp. 1362-1374, 2021, doi: 10.33996/revistahorizontes.v5i21.281.
- [53] J. Anicama, «Influencia de la gamificación en el rendimiento académico de los estudiantes de psicología de la Universidad Autónoma del Perú», *Acta Psicológica Peruana*, vol. 5, n.º 2, pp. 230-247, 2020, [En línea]. Disponible en: <http://revistas.autonoma.edu.pe/index.php/ACPP/article/view/296>